
Deliverable
D-JIP2-4.8 Report section
about user requirements,
relevant modelling
modules and final
specification for a
modelling tool
Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: BfR

Contributing partners:

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Other contributors	
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REPORT

Report section about user requirements, relevant modelling modules and final specification for a modelling tool

In order to assess and evaluate health risks of substances, microorganisms, products and processes, a risk assessment is necessary. The exposure assessment for biological, chemical or physical agents aims at quantifying the frequency and level of exposure for the population or for defined population groups. For this purpose, numerous information must be linked, e.g. data on the origin and distribution of the noxae, the resulting occurrence in the relevant contact media (food, products, environment), information on the behaviour of the exposed individuals (e.g. contact time or consumption behaviour etc.) as well as personal constellations (e.g. height, weight, age etc.). The results of the exposure estimation are compared with the hazard estimation in the process of risk characterisation, e.g. in the form of a health-related exposure threshold. From this, the extent to which the safe exposure has been exceeded and thus the risk of a health effect can be derived. A prototype of a web application is developed at the BfR to support risk assessors in the creation and documentation of quantitative risk models.

Our goal is to develop a platform-independent risk modelling framework / web application. Before we started the further technical development of our statistical web application we tried to obtain information on the requirements of the users. We asked people inside our department and people from cooperations within the One health EJP project who are involved and worked with quantitative microbiological risk analysis. We had to notice that the list of requirements was huge.

The main user requirements were appealing and quickly understandable design of application that works universally. But also interactive elements within the application and a user interface that is as simple as possible and as versatile as necessary. Another important point was that data which are involved in the process of risk modelling within the web application are not to be saved on the application server due to data protection laws. In addition, the platform-independent risk modeling framework must ensure that all results have a contentual and mathematical correctness.

Further important and relevant modelling modules for quantitative microbiological risk assessment have been identified for our web application. This includes the mathematical module of the distribution fitting to data or percentile with a wide range of distributions. Another important modelling module is the one- and two dimensional monte-carlo-simulation technique. Quantitative risk analysis should reflect the variability in the risk and take into account the uncertainty associated with the risk estimate. A Monte-Carlo simulation should be useful to point out the variability and uncertainty in the modelled risk. To test the robustness of the results of a model in the presence of uncertainty, our application should include a module of sensitivity analysis that increases the understanding of the relationships between input and output variables in a model.

More features of web application should be a standardized report in PDF format and comprehensive documentation and characterization of the mathematical model used. Further features are the ability to save, upload and download a session or a model. It would be also very helpful that the application is harmonized with other software applications and has a quick understandable help page.

Additionally, it was required to write the whole application in R, as all our mathematical packages are written in R. So we decided and developed a prototype of risk modelling framework in R shiny for quantitative microbiological risk assessment. To make the web application easily available we are currently working on stable online version and validate our prototyp.